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NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION USING HIDDEN MARKOV MODEL (HMM)

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ABSTRACT:

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is the subtask of Natural Language Processing (NLP) which is the branch of artificial intelligence. It has many applications mainly in machine translation, text to speech synthesis, natural language understanding, Information Extraction, Information retrieval, question answering etc. The aim of NER is to classify words into some predefined categories like location name, person name, organization name, date, time etc. In this paper we describe the Hidden Markov Model (HMM) based approach of machine learning in detail to identify the named entities. The main idea behind the use of HMM model for building NER system is that it is language independent and we can apply this system for any language domain. In our NER system the states are not fixed means it is of dynamic in nature one can use it according to their interest. The corpus used by our NER system is also not domain specific.

KEYWORDS

Named Entity Recognition (NER), Natural Language processing (NLP), Hidden Markov Model (HMM).

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RESUME INFORMATION EXTRACTION WITH A NOVEL TEXT BLOCK SEGMENTATION ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, we have witnessed the rapid development of deep neural networks and distributed representations in natural language processing. However, the applications of neural networks in resume parsing lack systematic investigation. In this study, we proposed an end-to-end pipeline for resume parsing based on neural networks-based classifiers and distributed embeddings. This pipeline leverages the position-wise line information and integrated meanings of each text block. The coordinated line classification by both line type classifier and line label classifier effectively segment a resume into predefined text blocks. Our proposed pipeline joints the text block segmentation with the identification of resume facts in which various sequence labelling classifiers perform named entity recognition within labelled text blocks. Comparative evaluation of four sequence labelling classifiers confirmed BLSTMCNNs-CRF's superiority in named entity recognition task. Further comparison among three publicized resume parsers also determined the effectiveness of our text block classification method.

KEYWORDS

Resume Parsing, Word Embeddings, Named Entity Recognition, Text Classifier, Neural Networks

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SURVEY OF MACHINE TRANSLATION SYSTEMS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The work in the area of machine translation has been going on for last few decades but the promising translation work began in the early 1990s due to advanced research in Artificial Intelligence and Computational Linguistics. India is a multilingual and multicultural country with over 1.25 billion population and 22 constitutionally recognized languages which are written in 12 different scripts. This necessitates the automated machine translation system for English to Indian languages and among Indian languages so as to exchange the information amongst people in their local language. Many usable machine translation systems have been developed and are under development in India and around the world. The paper focuses on different approaches used in the development of Machine Translation Systems and also briefly described some of the Machine Translation Systems along with their features, domains and limitations.

KEYWORDS

Machine Translation, Example-based MT, Transfer-based MT, Interlingua-based MT

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GRAMMAR CHECKERS FOR NATURAL LANGUAGES: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Natural Language processing is an interdisciplinary branch of linguistic and computer science studied under the Artificial Intelligence (AI) that gave birth to an allied area called 'Computational Linguistics' which focuses on processing of natural languages on computational devices. A natural language consists of many sentences which are meaningful linguistic units involving one or more words linked together in accordance with a set of predefined rules called 'grammar'. Grammar checking is fundamental task in the formal world that validates sentences syntactically as well as semantically. Grammar Checker tool is a prominent tool within language engineering. Our review draws on the till date development of various Natural Language grammar checkers to look at past, present and the future in the present context. Our review covers common grammatical errors , overview of grammar checking process, grammar checkers of various languages with the aim of seeking their approaches, methodologies and performance evaluation, which would be great help for developing new tool and system as a whole. The survey concludes with the discussion of different features included in existing grammar checkers of foreign languages as well as a few Indian Languages.

KEYWORDS

Natural Language Processing, Computational Linguistics, Writing errors, Grammatical mistakes, Grammar Checker

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MACHINE TRANSLATION DEVELOPMENT FOR INDIAN LANGUAGES AND ITS APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a survey of Machine translation system for Indian Regional languages. Machine translation is one of the central areas of Natural language processing (NLP). Machine translation (henceforth referred as MT) is important for breaking the language barrier and facilitating inter-lingual communication. For a multilingual country like INDIA which is largest democratic country in whole world, there is a big requirement of automatic machine translation system. With the advent of Information Technology many documents and web pages are coming up in a local language so there is a large need of good MT systems to address all these issues in order to establish a proper communication between states and union governments to exchange information amongst the people of different states. This paper focuses on different Machine translation projects done in India along with their features and domain.

KEYWORDS

Machine translation, computational linguistics, Indian Languages, Rule-based, Statistical, Empirical MT, Principle-based, Knowledge-based, Hybrid

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SURVEY ON MACHINE TRANSLITERATION AND MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Globalization and growth of Internet users truly demands for almost all internet based applications to support local languages. Support of local languages can be given in all internet based applications by means of Machine Transliteration and Machine Translation. This paper provides the thorough survey on machine transliteration models and machine learning approaches used for machine transliteration over the period of more than two decades for internationally used languages as well as Indian languages. Survey shows that linguistic approach provides better results for the closely related languages and probability based statistical approaches are good when one of the languages is phonetic and other is nonphonetic. Better accuracy can be achieved only by using Hybrid and Combined models.

KEYWORDS

CRF, Grapheme, HMM, Machine Transliteration, Machine Learning, NCM, Phoneme, SVM

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SENTIMENT ANALYSIS ON PRODUCT FEATURES BASED ON LEXICON APPROACH USING NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Sentiment analysis has played an important role in identifying what other people think and what their behavior is. Text can be used to analyze the sentiment and classified as positive, negative or neutral. Applying the sentiment analysis on the product reviews on e-market helps not only the customer but also the industry people for taking decision. The method which provides sentiment analysis about the individual product's features is discussed here. This paper presents the use of Natural Language Processing and SentiWordNet in this interesting application in Python: 1. Sentiment Analysis on Product review [Domain: Electronic]2. sentiment analysis regarding the product's feature present in the product review [Sub Domain: Mobile Phones]. It uses a lexicon based approach in which text is tokenized for calculating the sentiment analysis of the product reviews on a e-market. The first part of paper includes sentiment analyzer which classifies the sentiment present in product reviews into positive, negative or neutral depending on the polarity. The second part of the paper is an extension to the first part in which the customer review's containing product's features will be segregated and then these separated reviews are classified into positive, negative and neutral using sentiment analysis. Here, mobile phones are used as the product with features as screen, processors, etc. This gives a business solution for users and industries for effective product decisions.

KEYWORDS

Sentiment Analysis, Natural Language Processing, SentiWordNet, lexicon based approach

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ALGORITHM FOR TEXT TO GRAPH CONVERSION AND SUMMARIZING USING NLP: A NEW APPROACH FOR BUSINESS SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Text can be analysed by splitting the text and extracting the keywords .These may be represented as summaries, tabular representation, graphical forms, and images. In order to provide a solution to large amount of information present in textual format led to a research of extracting the text and transforming the unstructured form to a structured format. The paper presents the importance of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and its two interesting applications in Python Language: 1. Automatic text summarization [Domain: Newspaper Articles] 2. Text to Graph Conversion [Domain: Stock news]. The main challenge in NLP is natural language understanding i.e. deriving meaning from human or natural language input which is done using regular expressions, artificial intelligence and database concepts. Automatic Summarization tool converts the newspaper articles into summary on the basis of frequency of words in the text. Text to Graph Converter takes in the input as stock article, tokenize them on various index (points and percent) and time and then tokens are mapped to graph. This paper proposes a business solution for users for effective time management.

KEYWORDS

NLP, Automatic Summarizer, Text to Graph Converter, Data Visualization, Regular Expression, Artificial Intelligence

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AMBIGUITY RESOLUTION IN INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

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ABSTRACT

With the advancement of the web it is very difficult to keep up with the amplifying requirements of learning on web, to satisfy user's expectation. Users demand with the updated and accurate results. To solve the queries Search Engines use different techniques. Google the most famous search engine uses Page Ranking Algorithm. Ranking Algorithms arrange the results according to the user's needs. This paper deals with "Page Rank Algorithm". Our proposed algorithm is an extension of page rank algorithm which refines the results so that user gets what he/she expects. We have used a measure Average Precision to compare Page Rank algorithm and the proposed algorithm, and proved that our algorithm provides better results.

KEYWORDS

Information retrieval, page ranking algorithms, weighted page rank

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HINDI AND MARATHI TO ENGLISH MACHINE transliteration USING SVM

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ABSTRACT

Language transliteration is one of the important areas in NLP. Transliteration is very useful for converting the named entities (NEs) written in one script to another script in NLP applications like Cross Lingual Information Retrieval (CLIR), Multilingual Voice Chat Applications and Real Time Machine Translation (MT). The most important requirement of Transliteration system is to preserve the phonetic properties of source language after the transliteration in target language. In this paper, we have proposed the named entity transliteration for Hindi to English and Marathi to English language pairs using Support Vector Machine (SVM). In the proposed approach, the source named entity is segmented into transliteration units; hence transliteration problem can be viewed as sequence labeling problem. The classification of phonetic units is done by using the polynomial kernel function of Support Vector Machine (SVM). Proposed approach uses phonetic of the source language and n-gram as two features for transliteration.

KEYWORDS

Machine Transliteration, n-gram, Support Vector Machine, Syllabification

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